

APPLICATION OF GEOSSET IN AUTOMOBILE CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract : This in the article car on the roads to the coating geogrid used about information,road in construction from the geogrid use, geosetka materials preparation technology such as issues illuminated .

Key words : Geosetka, geosetka application, polymer compound, plastic mixtures, geosetka sizes of asphalt concrete mechanic property of the geogrid.

Sign in. Republic road farm state by manage in the system competition environment formation and to the network investments attraction to be done hindrance doing series problems and disadvantages there is. Road farm of management modern system creation, control and economy functions sure limitation, from monopoly issue, private sector enterprises attraction to do and investment attractiveness increase at the expense of healthy competition environment formation, way to the construction innovations wide current reach for the purpose of 2017-2021 Uzbekistan Republic development five priority direction according to Actions strategy tasks according to, December 9, 2019 on the date Uzbekistan Republic President of Uzbekistan Republic road economy system deep reform to do measures about Decree and - Road field manage system more to improve about measures about The decision acceptance done. the world from experience come out today in the day asphalt concrete coated car ways work the term extension, cover external effect as a result own feature save stay and athletics of means coming loading acceptance in doing defects appear to be reduce problems in solving one how many in the direction scientific research take is going.

Main part From geogrids made from films of use main purpose asphalt concrete layers of coating valence temperature and do not bend to stress durability increase, crack in the zone contact conditions change and that's it basically of coating service to do the term is to multiply of the project two option choose recommendation will be :

- mainly temperature to the effect durability increase for geoset asphalt concrete of coating high and bottom between the layers (layer). lay down blocking foundation and asphalt concrete between layers (layer). geoset laying , basically to the effect of temporary load durability increase Layered in layers strengthening from geogrids use of the corridor service to do 1.5-2 times its time increases , to this according to to patches spent of work volume by 30-50% decreases.

Flat on the surface pavement short term static load as from the wheels pressure spends Motor transport uneven surface on when moving , on the cover the wheel pressure increases or decreases, that is dynamic. Plastic deformations number increase and asphalt concrete of coating no to be done acceleration of traffic flow increase with depend From geosynthetics right use of roads quality improve and work the term extension, labor spending reduce and construction the time shorten methods one is weather, climate and exploitation conditions depends it's not .

Geosynthetic materials is usually synthetic as well as other kind of raw from materials (mineral, glass or basalt fibers and others) taken, folded compact in form (rolls, blocks, plates and others) additional materials Create for intended construction materials class Different in construction (transport, civil engineering , hydraulic engineering). purposes (strengthening, drainage, protection making, filtering, waterproofing , heat isolation) and the following materials groups own into received layers (layers): geotextile materials, geosesh Grids, geocomposites, geoshells, geomembranes , geoplates and geoelements . Weak diaper soil strengthening for road of the cake basis lifting geo- fabric (woven and woven), geosets (woven , knitted and plastic extruded) is used .

Modern construction methods have been roads for from geotextiles use guarantee gives : construction 25% savings on materials ; of water prevention get construction connect reliability .

Road for from the geogrid use of bridges the work activities improve and costs by 45 percent reduce enable will give . The work during geogrid deformation to the process high resistance shows .

On the roads holes modern repair corridors in placement used of materials work the term to multiply aspiration Demand does

1 . Road coating in repair geoset apply

Geogrids are also widespread gone materials in separation (for example , sand and gravel) geonetka to the cells down the rest rough fractional filler from substance consists of border layer formation because of increased going viscosity increase for is used (Fig. 1).

Own in turn , hard waterproofing layers formation for invalid has been weaving non -geo- bands drainage layer harvest to do for more is used . Second without , geomembranes good Geosynthetics in choosing main task object in construction his the role is necessary functionality (strengthening , separation , drainage , filtering , erosion protection do) and suitable coming physical mechanic features sure is to

determine . Wrong selected in the case of , synthetic from the material use effect than expected difference to do can

It should be noted that by using new materials and improving their properties, the constructions of highway pavements are improved and they achieve a certain level of efficiency. Some of the efficiencies are achieved by reducing the volume of materials used in road surface construction (see Figure 2), and some by increasing the service life (see Figure 3).

2 . Reducing material consumption by using geo s skirts

3 . Extending the period between repairs by applying ChMA

Along with mixtures made from new materials, geosetkani use The quality of the layer foundation built by the method high to strength achieves.

The following conclusion to do can: Gosetka work on the way out types of material used and and their work issuer materials analysis done. Car of the ways asphalt concrete coating geogrid materials with fortification method was studied and analysis done

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